

Table B.1. Observations for group one

PF-observations group one ordered by date							
#	Class	Date and time when raster started	Observation mode	CAD (sec)	FOV centre (arcsec)	OBSID	NOAA AR #
1	C5.9, M1.8, C7.4	2014-02-12T21:54:58	Large coarse 8-step raster	42	(140,-90)	3860257280	11974
2	X1.0	2014-03-29T14:09:38	Very large coarse 8-step raster	72	(490,282)	3860258481	12017
3	M3.9	2014-06-11T18:19:27	Medium coarse 8-step raster	21	(-781,-306)	3863605329	12087
4	M1.1	2014-09-06T11:23:39	Large sit-and-stare	9	(-709,-298)	3820259253	12157
5	X1.6	2014-09-10T11:28:25	Large sit-and-stare	9	(-137,125)	3860259453	12158
6	M8.7	2014-10-21T18:10:52	Large sit-and-stare	16	(-359,-316)	3860261353	12192
7	X1.6	2014-10-22T08:18:50	Very large coarse 8-step raster	131	(-292,-303)	3860261381	12192
8	C9.7, X1.0	2014-10-25T14:58:28	Large sit-and-stare	5	(408,-319)	3880106953	12192
9	M2.4, C8.3, M7.1						
10	M1.0, M1.3, C4.9, C9.6	2014-10-26T18:52:50	Large sit-and-stare	16	(648,-287)	3864111353	12192
11	C5.4, C4.6, M3.4, M6.6	2014-10-27T20:56:55	Large sit-and-stare	16	(779,-271)	3864111353	12192
12	M1.0	2014-11-07T09:37:26	Large coarse 16-step raster	23	(-646,224)	3860602088	12205
13	M1.8, C5.8	2015-03-11T04:46:03	Large coarse 8-step raster	75	(-430,-194)	3860259280	12297
14	X2.1, M1.0, C7.8	2015-03-11T15:19:47	Large coarse 4-step raster	16	(-353,-197)	3860107071	12297
15	C8.4, M1.6, M1.4	2015-03-12T05:45:19	Large sit-and-stare	5	(-185,-190)	3860107053	12297
16	M6.5	2015-06-22T17:00:03	Large sparse 16-step raster	33	(72,192)	3660100039	12371
17	M1.1	2015-08-21T16:01:15	Medium dense 32-step raster	102	(-467,-336)	3660104044	12403
AR-observations group one							
1		2014-03-13T09:35:21	Large sit-and-stare	9	(521,23)	3820109554	12003
2		2014-03-29T20:14:26	Medium sit-and-stare	17	(687,-166)	3820011652	12014
3		2014-11-28T21:05:38	Very large sit-and-stare	10	(-34,-322)	3860009154	12217
4		2014-12-01T15:44:38	Large sit-and-stare	10	(-80,-329)	3800008053	12222
5		2015-01-30T11:27:15	Very large dense 4-step raster	21	(-756,161)	3860607366	12277
6		2015-04-08T04:57:17	Large sit-and-stare	5	(45,-118)	3860107054	12320
7		2015-05-18T14:39:15	Large coarse 4-step raster	21	(300,-98)	3860256971	12346
8		2015-05-18T16:14:15	Large coarse 4-step raster	21	(315,-95)	3860256971	12346
9		2015-05-21T18:59:17	Very large sit-and-stare	5	(-382,398)	3800507454	12351
10		2015-07-03T16:59:17	Large sparse 8-step raster	45	(-186,213)	3620006130	12373
11		2015-07-04T10:09:21	Very large sit-and-stare	9	(86,174)	3860108354	12373
12		2015-07-04T16:59:17	Large sparse 8-step raster	44	(20,202)	3620006130	12373
13		2015-07-24T05:35:23	Large sit-and-stare	9	(557,-204)	3620109103	12387
14		2015-07-28T15:18:49	Medium coarse 4-step raster	37	(-227,-289)	3660109122	12389
15		2015-08-07T22:14:21	Large coarse 8-step raster	74	(547,125)	3860259180	12394
16		2015-08-09T06:15:51	Large coarse 8-step raster	75	(-236,-370)	3860009180	12394
17		2015-09-16T18:17:44	Medium coarse 16-step raster	34	(-564,-356)	3600101141	12418
18		2015-10-17T00:31:15	Large sit-and-stare	3	(-558,-233)	3660105403	12434

Table B.2. PF-observations group two

PF-observations group two ordered by date							
#	Class	Date and time when raster started	Observation mode	CAD (sec)	FOV centre (arcsec)	OBSID	NOAA AR #
17	C4.5	2014-01-05T01:33:38	Large coarse 8-step raster	76	(-637,-107)	3860257480	11944
18	C6.6	2014-01-05T14:34:22	Large coarse 8-step raster	68	(-544,-126)	3860257480	11944
19	C9.7	2014-02-02T11:05:21	Very large coarse 8-step raster	30	(600,-93)	3860259281	11969
20	M1.3	2014-02-05T15:39:21	Large coarse 8-step raster	39	(498,-123)	3860259280	11967
21	C7.4	2014-07-10T20:33:29	Very large sparse 64-step raster	27	(-417,88)	3860358143	12113
22	M1.5	2014-08-01T17:20:59	Large dense 64-step raster	7	(-201,-233)	3800013190	12127
23	C7.1	2014-08-31T11:08:41	Large sit-and-stare	1	(750,85)	3820259353	12149
24	C6.3	2014-09-04T11:24:56	Large sit-and-stare	1	(526,-345)	3820259253	12152
25	C4.6	2014-09-07T23:59:47	Large coarse 64-step raster	11	(-475,-322)	3820113694	12157
26	M1.0	2014-09-28T12:09:36	Large coarse 2-step raster	1800	(317,-267)	3860359362	12172
27	C6.7	2014-10-17T14:56:45	Large coarse 8-step raster	435	(-167,123)	3860354980	12192
28	C4.7	2014-10-19T14:59:35	Large coarse 8-step raster	425	(-744,-265)	3860354980	12192
29	C9.2	2014-10-25T07:00:00	Very large dense raster	1	(261,-302)	3820260096	12192
30	C4.6	2014-10-25T09:00:38	Large sit-and-stare	1	(354,-303)	3860259353	12192
31	C8.4, C9.5, X2.0	2014-10-25T23:01:38	Large sit-and-stare	1	(444,-300)	3864109353	12192
32	M1.0	2014-10-26T15:31:58	Large sit-and-stare	1	(587,-306)	3880106953	12192
33	C5.3, M1.6	2014-10-28T10:09:46	Very large sparse 64-step raster	30	(850,-265)	3801259593	12192
34	C6.7	2015-03-11T22:47:58	Large coarse 4-step raster	865	(-301,-201)	3860107071	12297
35	C4.8, M2.7	2015-03-12T17:50:36	Large sit-and-stare	1	(-139,-193)	3860107053	12297
36	M1.8, C6.9	2015-03-13T04:59:56	Large sit-and-stare	1	(9,-154)	3860109053	12297
37	C6.2	2015-03-13T17:28:05	Large sit-and-stare	1	(110,-161)	3860109053	12297
38	C7.9	2015-04-10T07:29:17	Large sit-and-stare	1	(472,-122)	3820257453	12320
39	C5.0	2015-05-07T16:46:39	Large coarse 8-step raster	125	(-750,264)	3860260280	12339
40	C5.6	2015-06-24T11:14:19	Large dense 4-step raster	960	(478,176)	3620106017	12371
41	M1.2	2015-08-20T23:40:44	Medium dense 32-step raster	420	(-583,-313)	3605202144	12401
42	C8.0	2015-08-27T23:09:50	Large coarse 4-step raster	460	(770,-289)	3660609323	12403
43	M2.1	2015-09-20T11:09:21	Medium sit-and-stare	1	(663,-386)	3680088902	12415
44	C4.5	2015-10-17T10:49:17	Large sparse 8-step raster	360	(-439,-247)	3620257130	12434
45	M3.7	2015-11-04T12:50:26	Large coarse 16-step raster	85	(37,61)	3660604042	12443
46	C7.8	2015-12-26T04:38:28	Large sit-and-stare	1	(-337,-336)	3680088903	12473
47	C8.0	2017-06-02T17:02:42	Large coarse 16-step raster	214	(-801,88)	3662506342	12661
48	C5.3	2017-07-09T07:10:45	Large sparse 32-step raster	16	(-567,-150)	3690215148	12665
49	M3.7	2017-09-09T05:19:58	Medium sit-and-stare	1	(883,-187)	3680108902	12673
50	C7.3	2021-08-27T19:25:58	Very large coarse 16-step raster	111	(-70,-542)	3602506443	12860
51	C8.3	2021-09-08T16:16:59	Very large sit-and-stare	1	(-172,-376)	3603013104	12866
52	M1.8	2021-09-23T13:09:08	Very large dense 320-step raster	3	(-249,-529)	3620108077	12871

Table B.3. AR-observations for group two

AR-observations group two ordered by date						
#	Date and time when raster started	Observation mode	CAD (sec)	FOV centre (arcsec)	OBSID	NOAA AR #
19	2014-03-02T23:03:41	Very large sparse 16-step raster	25	(29,-87)	3810263287	11990
20	2014-11-24T17:41:20	Very large sit-and-stare	1	(-759,-175)	3860259254	12209
21	2015-12-05T22:52:50	Large coarse 4-step raster	165	(-759,-175)	3610107123	12463
22	2016-09-10T12:09:30	Large sparse 64-step raster	5	(804,74)	3810263287	12585
23	2016-09-20T12:24:29	Large sparse 64-step raster	23	(159,1)	3630010059	12593
24	2016-10-28T21:22:47	Large sparse 64-step raster	6	(158,21)	3630010059	12604
25	2017-01-28T17:02:17	Large coarse 32-step raster	15	(844,244)	3630256051	12628
26	2018-02-27T10:55:39	Very large coarse 16-step raster	60	(298,211)	3610108043	12700
27	2022-02-01T16:59:21	Large coarse 8-step raster	46	(-748,-206)	3660259533	12939
28	2022-02-08T21:24:21	Very large dense 320-step raster	1	(-176,493)	3620108077	12941
29	2022-02-09T23:19:21	Large coarse 8-step raster	41	(14,492)	3660259533	12941
30	2022-02-12T15:54:39	Large coarse 8-step raster	60	(559,472)	3660259533	12941

Appendix C: Complete results**Table C.1.** Result table experiments Mg II *h&k*.

Line	Experiment	Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	ROCSS	TSS
Mg II <i>h&k</i>	Experiment validset 1				
	Single Layer	0.847±0.055	0.695±0.110	0.694±0.11	0.695±0.110
	Two Layers	0.847±0.055	0.694±0.110	0.694±0.11	0.694±0.110
	Three Layers	0.854±0.055	0.707±0.111	0.708±0.11	0.707±0.111
	ConvNet	0.856±0.051	0.713±0.101	0.714±0.102	0.713±0.101
	Experiment testset 1				
	Single Layer	0.721±0.021	0.441±0.041	0.442±0.042	0.441±0.041
	Two Layers	0.716±0.021	0.433±0.042	0.432±0.042	0.433±0.042
	Three Layers	0.719±0.020	0.437±0.040	0.438±0.04	0.437±0.040
	ConvNet	0.720±0.020	0.441±0.039	0.440±0.04	0.441±0.039
	Experiment validset 2				
	Single Layer	0.693±0.071	0.386±0.142	0.386±0.142	0.386±0.142
	Two Layers	0.696±0.070	0.392±0.140	0.392±0.140	0.392±0.140
	Three Layers	0.697±0.073	0.395±0.147	0.394±0.146	0.395±0.147
	ConvNet	0.694±0.074	0.388±0.148	0.388±0.148	0.388±0.148
	Experiment testset 2				
	Single Layer	0.803±0.009	0.606±0.019	0.606±0.036	0.606±0.019
	Two Layers	0.797±0.018	0.594±0.036	0.594±0.036	0.594±0.036
	Three Layers	0.799±0.017	0.598±0.035	0.598±0.034	0.598±0.035
	ConvNet	0.800±0.014	0.600±0.027	0.600±0.028	0.600±0.027
	All Observations				
	Single Layer	0.762±0.019	0.523±0.038	0.524±0.038	0.523±0.039
	Two Layers	0.766±0.020	0.531±0.041	0.530±0.04	0.531±0.040
	Three Layers	0.765±0.019	0.531±0.040	0.530±0.04	0.531±0.039
	ConvNet	0.767±0.019	0.533±0.037	0.532±0.038	0.533±0.037

Table C.2. Result table experiments Si IV.

Line	Experiment	Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	ROCSS	TSS
Si IV	Experiment validset 1				
	Single Layer	0.699±0.070	0.399±0.139	0.398±0.14	0.399±0.139
	Two Layers	0.710±0.060	0.420±0.119	0.420±0.12	0.420±0.119
	Three Layers	0.714±0.073	0.427±0.146	0.428±0.146	0.427±0.146
	ConvNet	0.728±0.103	0.456±0.205	0.456±0.206	0.456±0.205
	Experiment testset 1				
	Single Layer	0.592±0.040	0.184±0.081	0.184±0.080	0.184±0.081
	Two Layers	0.604±0.037	0.208±0.073	0.208±0.074	0.208±0.073
	Three Layers	0.602±0.047	0.204±0.095	0.204±0.092	0.204±0.095
	ConvNet	0.646±0.044	0.291±0.089	0.292±0.088	0.291±0.089
	Experiment validset 2				
	Single Layer	0.731±0.034	0.462±0.067	0.462±0.068	0.461±0.067
	Two Layers	0.735±0.038	0.469±0.077	0.470±0.076	0.469±0.077
	Three Layers	0.739±0.034	0.477±0.067	0.468±0.068	0.477±0.067
	ConvNet	0.720±0.054	0.439±0.107	0.440±0.108	0.439±0.107
	Experiment testset 2				
	Single Layer	0.624±0.058	0.249±0.117	0.248±0.116	0.249±0.117
	Two Layers	0.627±0.067	0.254±0.134	0.254±0.134	0.254±0.134
	Three Layers	0.631±0.061	0.263±0.122	0.262±0.122	0.263±0.122
	ConvNet	0.606±0.089	0.212±0.177	0.212±0.178	0.212±0.177
	All Observations				
	Single Layer	0.697±0.053	0.394±0.107	0.394±0.108	0.394±0.107
	Two Layers	0.709±0.053	0.418±0.106	0.418±0.106	0.418±0.106
	Three Layers	0.712±0.055	0.424±0.110	0.712±0.11	0.424±0.109
	ConvNet	0.721±0.070	0.442±0.139	0.424±0.14	0.442±0.139

Table C.3. Result table experiments C II.

Line	Experiment	Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	ROCSS	TSS
C II	Experiment validset 1				
	Single Layer	0.716±0.073	0.433±0.147	0.432±0.148	0.433±0.147
	Two Layers	0.744±0.068	0.488±0.135	0.488±0.136	0.488±0.135
	Three Layers	0.743±0.061	0.486±0.123	0.486±0.122	0.485±0.123
	ConvNet	0.759±0.083	0.519±0.165	0.518±0.166	0.519±0.165
	Experiment testset 1				
	Single Layer	0.54±0.022	0.079±0.044	0.08±0.044	0.079±0.044
	Two Layers	0.563±0.012	0.125±0.024	0.126±0.024	0.125±0.024
	Three Layers	0.567±0.016	0.133±0.032	0.134±0.032	0.133±0.032
	ConvNet	0.559±0.03	0.118±0.060	0.118±0.06	0.118±0.060
	Experiment validset 2				
	Single Layer	0.559±0.061	0.117±0.123	0.118±0.122	0.117±0.123
	Two Layers	0.576±0.060	0.153±0.121	0.152±0.12	0.153±0.121
	Three Layers	0.583±0.057	0.166±0.115	0.166±0.114	0.166±0.115
	ConvNet	0.578±0.074	0.157±0.149	0.156±0.148	0.157±0.149
	Experiment testset 2				
	Single Layer	0.578±0.042	0.155±0.084	0.156±0.084	0.155±0.084
	Two Layers	0.589±0.046	0.178±0.09	0.178±0.092	0.178±0.09
	Three Layers	0.578±0.060	0.156±0.12	0.156±0.12	0.156±0.12
	ConvNet	0.576±0.060	0.153±0.12	0.152±0.12	0.153±0.12
	All Observations				
	Single Layer	0.671±0.035	0.343±0.07	0.342±0.07	0.343±0.07
	Two Layers	0.689±0.039	0.379±0.078	0.378±0.078	0.379±0.078
	Three Layers	0.693±0.044	0.385±0.088	0.386±0.088	0.385±0.088
	ConvNet	0.708±0.045	0.416±0.089	0.416±0.09	0.416±0.089

Table C.4. Results combining the three spectral lines.

Experiment		Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	ROCSS	TSS
Three lines with self learned features	Single Layer	0.766±0.067	0.513±0.137	0.528±0.138	0.528±0.139
	Two Layers	0.767±0.068	0.517±0.138	0.534±0.138	0.534±0.137
	Three Layers	0.766±0.069	0.514±0.138	0.530±0.140	0.529±0.14
Self learned features only Mg	Single Layer	0.727±0.054	0.442±0.107	0.464±0.108	0.463±0.108
	Two Layers	0.726±0.054	0.440±0.106	0.462±0.108	0.462±0.107
Three lines with newly learned features	Single Layer	0.755±0.023	0.509±0.047	0.510±0.046	0.509±0.047
	Two Layers	0.753±0.024	0.506±0.048	0.506±0.048	0.506±0.048
	Three Layers	0.753±0.022	0.507±0.046	0.506±0.044	0.507±0.046